

**MODELS AND METHODS FOR
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF
INNOVATIVE RESEARCH**

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SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING ECONOMIC THINKING IN STUDENTS

Nishonova Dilafruz Komilovna

Teacher of the Department of General Education, New Age University

e-mail: dilafruzkomilova13@gmail.com

Abstract. This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of the process of forming and developing economic thinking in students. Economic thinking is the ability of students to understand, analyze and consciously respond to economic phenomena. The study shows effective ways to integrate economic knowledge in the educational process, use interactive methods, and form economic thinking through real-life examples. It also highlights the importance of teacher activity, learning environment, and social experience in developing economic thinking in students.

Keywords: economic thinking, student, economic education, economic knowledge, interactive method, development of thinking, educational process, economic consciousness.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o'quvchilarda iqtisodiy tafakkurni shakllantirish va rivojlantirish jarayonining nazariy hamda amaliy jihatlari tahlil qilinadi. Iqtisodiy tafakkur – bu o'quvchilarning iqtisodiy hodisalarni anglash, tahlil qilish va ularga ongli munosabat bildirish qobiliyatini ifodalaydi. Tadqiqotda ta'lim jarayonida iqtisodiy bilimlarni integratsiyalash, interfaol metodlardan foydalanish, hayotiy misollar orqali iqtisodiy fikrlashni shakllantirishning samarali yo'llari ko'rsatib berilgan. Shuningdek, o'quvchilarda iqtisodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishda o'qituvchi faoliyatining, o'quv muhitining va ijtimoiy tajribaning ahamiyati yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy tafakkur, o'quvchi, iqtisodiy ta'lim, iqtisodiy bilim, interfaol metod, tafakkurni rivojlantirish, o'qitish jarayoni, iqtisodiy ong.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются теоретические и практические аспекты формирования и развития экономического мышления студентов. Экономическое мышление – это способность студентов понимать, анализировать и осознанно реагировать на экономические явления. В исследовании показаны эффективные способы интеграции экономических знаний в образовательный процесс, использования интерактивных методов и формирования экономического мышления на примерах из реальной жизни. Также подчеркивается важность деятельности преподавателя, учебной среды и социального опыта в развитии экономического мышления студентов.

Ключевые слова: экономическое мышление, студент, экономическое образование, экономические знания, интерактивный метод, развитие мышления, образовательный процесс, экономическое сознание.

Introduction. One of the most important tasks of the education system in modern society is to form economic thinking, economic culture and a socially active life position in students. In today's globalization process, economic knowledge and skills are becoming one of the main factors determining the life competence of each person.

In particular, the need to introduce economic education in a targeted and systematic manner from the primary grades is recognized as one of the urgent issues in pedagogical theory and practice.

Today, in a market economy, one of the main tasks of the education system is to equip the younger generation not only with theoretical knowledge, but also with the economic thinking necessary in practical life. Because economic thinking plays an important role in helping students make the right decisions in everyday life, use financial resources rationally, and correctly understand and analyze economic processes taking place in society.

Today, the development of society, the sustainable development of the national economy, and the well-being of people directly depend on the level of economic thinking. Economic thinking is a person's ability to understand, analyze economic phenomena and processes, make rational decisions and apply them in practice. It is clearly manifested in a person's daily life, labor activity, consumer culture and entrepreneurial initiatives.

The education system plays a leading role in the development of economic thinking. Economic knowledge, practical exercises, participation in socio-economic relations provided during the educational process enrich the individual's thinking and form the ability to make independent decisions. At the same time, the family environment, the media, social networks, the specific features of state policy and market relations also serve as important factors in the development of economic thinking.

The study of this topic helps to educate young people in an economically conscious, responsible, thrifty and entrepreneurial spirit. Therefore, identifying the factors affecting the development of economic thinking and effectively managing them is relevant today not only theoretically, but also practically.

In this regard, legal mechanisms are also important in our country, and it is important to protect this by law. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ORQ-901 "On the Status of a Pedagogue" was also adopted on February 1, 2024, which defines the processes by which teachers can improve the results of education and upbringing of students in the educational process, especially in the process of imparting economic knowledge, and bring factors influencing the development of economic thinking into a holistic system.

The development of economic thinking depends on many factors, among which educational, social, psychological, technological and cultural factors are of particular importance. Effective teaching of economic knowledge in school education, the formation of economic values in the family environment, as well as the ability of students to think and analyze independently determine the level of their economic thinking.

Also, the expansion of digital technologies and information resources is increasing the interest of young people in economic processes and creating conditions for them to acquire practical skills. From this point of view, the formation of economic thinking in students is one of the priority areas of the educational process.

Literature analysis. Many scientists have conducted research on the

pedagogical possibilities of forming economic culture in students, factors influencing the development of economic thinking and their characteristics. As a result, pedagogical possibilities have also increased. One of the scientists of our country, D.Sh.Otabaeva, has found this out in her scientific research and pedagogical views. The main views of scientists are that they conducted research on innovative pedagogical technologies for providing economic education to students (on the example of primary grades).

Another of our scientists, D. Karamatova and M. Ravshanova, also reveal in their research the role of pedagogical technologies in the formation of economic education in young students, the role of economic education in the development of economic thinking of young people, the characteristics of factors influencing the development of economic thinking. They also give their thoughts on the formation and working processes of the methodology for the effective use of economic education in the development of economic thinking of young people.

The CIS countries also play a high role in this regard. After all, the issues of forming economic culture and economic thinking are constantly emerging as topical issues in them. A.A. Laskin also reflects the results of his research on the pedagogical principles and conditions, influencing factors of economic thinking among students in higher educational institutions.

In the development of economic thinking, the historical roots of economic education - the immortal works inherited from our great ancestors - serve as an invaluable source for us. The formation of economic thought in Central Asia is inextricably linked with the names of the great encyclopedists-scholars and thinkers - Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Al-Biruni, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Alisher Navoi, Zahridin Muhammad Babur and others.

Another scientist, N.S. Kovaleva, in her research, explained the formation of economic science, the structure of the economy, its laws, categories, property relations, factors of production, needs, savings, economic growth and the general foundations of the economy related to resources in theoretical and practical terms, as well as the analysis of factors affecting the development of economic competencies of future specialists in socio-cultural activities.

Research methodology. In conducting the research, methods such as scientific research, induction and deduction, expert assessment, observation, survey, modeling, systematization, comparison and comparison, and analysis were used to reveal the true essence of the topic.

Analysis and results. The formation of economic culture and thinking in students is one of the urgent tasks of the education system today. Because in a market economy, the acquisition of economic knowledge and skills by young people determines their future professional activities, success in social life, and contribution to the development of society.

The formation of economic thinking in students is one of the important tasks of the modern educational process. Because in today's conditions of globalization and market economy, the acquisition of economic knowledge, skills and qualifications by young people, the ability to analyze economic processes and consciously respond to them is an important factor in the development of society.

Firstly, social factors play an important role in the development of economic thinking. The economic literacy of the family, the role of parents in their financial decisions and daily economic activities as an example for students, the level of economic culture in society, the economic values of various social groups form economic awareness and thinking in students.

Secondly, educational factors play a special role. High-quality teaching of subjects in which economic knowledge is taught in schools, the wide use of economic concepts and practical exercises in the curriculum, the use of innovative pedagogical approaches broaden the economic worldview of students. The professional skills and methodological training of the teacher also have a direct impact.

Thirdly, psychological and personal factors are also important in the development of economic thinking. Students' personal interests, motivation for economic knowledge, strong-willed qualities, ability to think independently and creatively determine the level of economic thinking.

Fourthly, technological and information factors are also gaining great importance today. The Internet, digital educational platforms, economic simulations, virtual laboratories allow students to study economic processes through practical experience. Also, economic information disseminated through the media and social networks also affects the economic thinking of young people.

Fifthly, cultural and national values directly affect the process of forming economic thinking in students. The economic traditions of our people, their attitude to labor, values such as thrift and honesty form the culture of making economic decisions in the minds of young people.

The development of economic thinking in students is a complex process, which is effectively carried out on the basis of a combination of education, family upbringing, personal motivation, information technologies and national values. Therefore, by increasing economic literacy in cooperation between school and family, providing economic experience through practical exercises and using innovative approaches, the opportunities for the formation of economic thinking in students are expanded.

The process of developing economic thinking in students depends on many internal and external factors, which play an important role in the formation of economic knowledge, skills and practical qualifications of the student. The analysis shows that in the development of economic thinking, on the one hand, pedagogical factors - the provision of economic knowledge in the educational process, interactive methods, the organization of practical exercises and projects - play an important role. On the other hand, social factors - family upbringing, the economic culture of parents, the social environment, the influence of the media and digital resources - give a significant result. Also, personal factors - the student's interest, aspirations, motivation for self-development - play a leading role in the formation of economic thinking. In conclusion, in order to effectively develop economic thinking, it is necessary to combine theory and practice in the educational process, prepare students for real-life situations, and direct them to entrepreneurship, responsibility, and thrift. The harmonious influence of pedagogical, social, and personal factors serves to form students as economically conscious, independent thinkers, and active participants in society.

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